

CO-OPERAS French workshop report

“FAIR data in SSH: needs and practices”

Paris, Feb. 3rd 2020

Summary

On February 3rd 2020, the GOFAIR CO-OPERAS Implementation Network held its 4th workshop on the definition of data for the FAIRification in Social Sciences and Humanities.

Although the workshop was primarily intended for researchers and PhDs in order to engage them in the FAIRification process, the audience gathered also a certain amount of technical experts. Perhaps more than in the other workshops, this led to a comprehensive overview of the FAIR needs and practices in the SSH field. Rather than defining the concept of data, the participants discussed very practical issues ranging from data sharing workflows, work environment organization, institutional policies and incentives.

This perspective provided interesting insights into the interconnection between various aspects, whether the interconnection is an implication or a contradiction. On one hand, for instance, increasing findability through standardization of data and metadata is highly dependent on the accessibility strategies and the target audiences. On the other hand, general policies in favor of openness conflict with legal gaps about specific data types and actual research practices. Therefore, not only the FAIR principles shouldn't be regarded as an isolated technical process, but the principles themselves should be applied in a consistent way taking into account these various levels and objectives.

Regarding data definition, the workshop's discussions also illustrated, with very detailed use cases, some of the specificities of SSH data, and more precisely the complexity of “datafication” in this field. From archive material to publications as project's outputs, and web-scraped data from social networks, the Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines, together and at the same time differently, offer a variety of technical, legal, and organizational challenges. As such, they are an excellent opportunity to test the FAIR principles flexibility and thus verify to what extent these can ensure the creation of an effective technical ecosystem for the open science.

Participants

The participants represented an interesting variety as per the disciplines, the types of data handled, the projects, their professional missions and their level of expertise. This led to fruitful exchanges not only with the organizers but also between the participants.

Below, the list of the disciplines represented, and where useful, the related data types:

- Archeology
- Archives / Images
- Communication Science / Music data
- Communication Science / Social networks
- Ethnology
- Literature
- Compared literature
- Sociology / Surveys

Focus group session: Data in SSH

In the field of music data, **already some interoperability exists through the use of MEI standard based on TEI**. It ensures possibility of exchanges between disciplines. However there are different levels of advancements: linguistics, for instance, are more mature. Furthermore, music data also contains artefacts, texts: they are “translated” through the standards.

FAIR principles: **at which step and how should the principles be applied in the process?**

In archeology, the data are included in a **captation process that “informs the data”** and implies a variety of types, range, and use. The use of standard is closely related to the dissemination and/or storage, often requiring standards to be achieved properly. In this context, **de facto standards emerge**. They can be transposed from another field (from land-use planning to geographical data).

Data accessibility can be ensured through storage and description on public national repositories (e.g. Nakala).

However, there is a **difference between dissemination** (in French: “diffusion”) **and outreach** (in French: “dissémination”): in parallel to the deposit of the “active data”, also indexing in broader and more accessible catalogues, and then storage on a public repository.

In geography, there are **few thematic repositories and generalist repositories (e.g. Zenodo) are not useful for the researchers**, so data is stored through other kind of services, especially Gitlab. There is a huge variety of type and provenance of the data: cartography, photos, twitter and socio-economic data. These data have uncertain legal and dissemination status due to the collection methods. For geography, the EC developed the standard INSPIRE which however doesn’t fit all the needs: the standard is thus being adapted by the community. The **researchers are scarcely involved in this work of standard implementation**, which is mostly taken in charge by the technical team. The researchers’ role is more to provide the interpretation of the data.

For Himalayan studies (ethnology, history, and other disciplines), **no existing standard is valuable for the data, especially because of alphabets’ transcription challenges**. The standards are thus developed directly by the research institutes. The community is however aiming at creating a single website, but it remains difficult to envision standards and descriptions which will answer to the needs of all the researchers. The researchers don’t engage much in the interoperability and findability processes: the **amount of time needed for the deposit of standardized data isn’t rewarded** in the French evaluation procedures. The effort of description and dissemination is thus mainly an individual matter.

For convenience, the researchers use a proprietary software (Adobe Lightroom) containing controlled vocabulary features. A project has been launched to develop a multilingual and multiscrypt vocabulary, supporting SKOS.

Furthermore, **accessibility to the data poses major ethics problems**: not only personal information but also pictures of individuals can put their life in danger (Tibetan situation). The individuals described or represented can be considered are the actual rightowners of these data.

A project focused on Art history archives stored in specific places aims at setting up a single portal with aligned metadata. These archives contains pictures of art taken by well-known Art historians: **what are the legal status and the usage licenses applicable** of this specific type of “data”? Some guidelines could be provided by Europeana. Moreover, these personal archives entail a large variety of types. Another specific project exists for a centralized deposit and normalized description on an institutional repository dedicated to SSH ([Didomena](#) from EHESS). The content of a single archive (IMEC) is currently being used as a proof-of-concept.

An alignment with the [CIDOC](#) ontology for cultural heritage has not yet been planned but could be envisioned.

Some questions arise around the deposit: **large scope repositories don't provide the description/discoverability granularity expected**; processes for large deposit are challenging.

For images, some complex multi-levels processes can be set up: use of international standards (EXIF, IPTC) as embedded metadata and then deposit on institutional repository (ODSAS from EHESS). As **metadata has to be embedded through a proprietary tool**, this is an issue for the dissemination and the alignment. It becomes especially complicated when **the alignment requires to use a non specialized controlled vocabulary** (French RAMEAU, equiv. to LCSH).

Metadata interoperability is challenged by the question of the linguistic scope, especially when the research deals with minor languages: **should the metadata be in the language of the data, of the researcher's institution or in English as a Lingua Franca?** This question relates with the dissemination objective: is the metadata linked to the data creation activity, to the dissemination within the discipline community or for a broader audience?

In the case of transdisciplinary project (e.g. Notre-Dame de Paris restoration), interoperability and accessibility are central but face a high heterogeneity of the data (photos, 3D point clouds, acoustic data, etc.). **Some guidance is required at the beginning of the project**: should the PIDs be applied to each file or only to each dataset, which access rights and usage licenses are applicable for each type of data, should there be one or many Data Management Plans for the project? A project-scale assessment is needed to **distinguish which data will be for internal use and which for broad dissemination**. A difference of roles will probably be made between the researchers creating the data and the institutions managing them.

The sociological researches conducted through the web has specificities that are not yet well addressed by the legal and organizational context. The **web-scraping of data is a well-spread, yet border-line practice** which implies various legal issues regarding data collection, reuse and dissemination. In fact, the Text and Data Mining legal framework is not well defined at the European level.

The **data collected by web-scraping is sometimes called “slim data”** because of its minimal level of description or provenance information. Furthermore, the low-standardized algorithms used for scraping and analysis are an obstacle for the research reproducibility (see [Beautiful soup](#) library).

The coexistence of the principle of openness and GDPR provisions about anonymisation can appear as contradictory injunctions: **is data fully anonymised fully reusable?** More

generally, the different aspects of technical standardization, usage licenses, public policies, citizen science are intertwined: a guidance action is required to address them in a coordinated fashion. An approach too much technical can be disconnected from the actual practices and methods.

As for the data, it is never “raw data”. **Metadata and descriptions are always a choice, be it conceptual, epistemological, political, etc.**

Another project illustrates one of the specificities of SSH research: the publication of texts. The works around the representation, expression and conception of contingency will rely on multiple types of resources and produce contents multiple as well. Moreover, **the published outputs will have a mixed status**: with respect to the project, they will be data to disseminate as openly as possible, but they will also overcome peer-review processes and, as publications, they will require thorough examination of their legal status. Important differences may appear between countries and disciplines. Pre-publication on public repositories (e.g. French HAL) may partly solve these issues.

More generally, **what is lacking is the recognition of the work needed for the dissemination** of the outputs. At the same time, this work is needed because of the French legal context and (see Loi pour une République Numérique, 2016 and the articles related to published outputs).

In relation with a network focused on digitalization and normalization of written texts, a work of standardization has been conducted (TEI transcription of writers' archives). The FAIRification is also somehow initiated through the attribution of PIDs and secure storage processes. For now, two distinct expressions of the digitized object exist, they will be interlinked in the future. DublinCore standard is used for the various types of data and an important objective throughout the process is to **ensure to maintain the richness of the metadata**.

The European project for an SSH open cloud (SSHOC) deals with survey data and is **already using a community-used standard, the Data Description Initiative**. The next step in this case will be to complete the missing informations with the researchers who created the data.

In conclusion, the participants outlined the questions raised by the Loi pour une République Numérique: some data types are not covered by the art. 30th provisions. **A lot of data outside of the legal scope are however being used** and the question of their formal retrieving through API remains open.

The participants also asked if, **how and by whom will the FAIR principles implementation be evaluated**. The organizer answered that, at this stage, it relies mainly on self-assessment tools or procedures. One example is the questionnaire used in the second session.

Workshop session: FAIR self-assessment

The participants were invited to answer to the questionnaire set up by the Australian Research Data Center (translation in French in Annex):

<https://ardc.edu.au/resources/working-with-data/fair-data/fair-self-assessment-tool/>.

The questionnaire is one example of the FAIR assessment wizards that are currently being developed (see esp. Data Stewardship Wizard at <https://ds-wizard.org/>).

The questionnaires detailed answers will be processed internally by the CO-OPERAS coordination team. A roundtable discussion allowed each participant to give feedback on the tool itself:

- Not complete enough, especially regarding reuse; there is a risk of indirect prescription: does reuse objective implies that embargo is impossible (but may be necessary for anonymisation process for instance).
- "PID of the data in every related metadata" seems a rather high level of expectation.
- The metadata format isn't addressed by the questionnaire.
- DMPs and esp. DMPs with guidelines are probably more useful are they are more detailed
- Who is the target of the questionnaire: for expert researcher, for IT manager, for Institution directors?
- Shouldn't the FAIR assessment in general be part of the project evaluation and made mandatory (by funders or evaluation national organization)? FAIRification incentives should be rewards for the work done.

Here are the main comments for the data of each project analyzed:

- the project already uses standards, RDF framework, but the aspects of permanence of metadata and provenance were not directly tackled yet with the project;
- interoperability standards already used but the question of findability through the identifier still to be set up;
- the question on access rights and usage licenses is interesting because of the variety of data, especially at the beginning of the project;
- some aspects already addressed thanks to the use of a metadata schema (DDI) but questions raised about the localization of the servers;
- questionnaire not always easy to answer when dealing only with metadata (harvesting);
- not totally adapted for new types of data: a corpus of web-scraping established through Zotero; non persistent data sources (e.g. blog) raise issues for findability and ownership rights management;
- depending on who answers the question, the result can vary significantly: some researchers store their data on hard drives.
- FAIR principles don't take language in consideration, while it is closely related to the dissemination's target;
- what is intended with "reusability"? Is it reuse by researchers, citizens, big companies?
- Data papers are not included in the questionnaire, while their promotion through FAIRification would facilitate the engagement from the researchers;
- the questionnaire doesn't ask for details regarding the versioning and more generally about long-term requirements;
- the machine-readable quality is less important than the possibility for humans to reuse the data;
- interesting tool to establish a state-of-the-art on data management: local storage vs metadata exposition in OAI-PMH repository, use of adapted standards vs thesaurus creation for texts typology, scarce information on provenance;

- for texts, reuse can occur at different levels, depending on the need: currently, 3 levels of structuration are provided (raw text, text with TEI structure, TEI with full metadata) corresponding to different potential usages.

Annex: FAIR self-assessment questionnaire in French

Discipline :	
Type :	
Des données...	
...Faciles à trouver	
Vos données ont-elles des identifiants ?	ID unique pérenne et citable
	URL
	ID local
	Pas d'ID
Est-ce que l'identifiant est présent dans toutes les métadonnées ?	Oui
	Non
Comment les métadonnées décrivent-elles les données ?	Avec un schéma reconnu de métadonnées et lisible par les machines
	Avec un schéma ad hoc de métadonnées (format texte)
	Titre et courte description
	Aucune description
Dans quel type d'entrepôt les données sont-elles stockées ?	Elles sont stockées en un seul endroit mais accessibles via plusieurs catalogues

	Un entrepôt public généraliste
	Un entrepôt disciplinaire
	Un entrepôt institutionnel local
	Dans aucun entrepôt
...Accessibles	
Les données sont-elles accessibles et de quelle façon ?	Accessibles sans restrictions
	Accessibles individuellement sous conditions (ex. acceptation d'une charte éthique)
	Une partie anonymisée ou modifiée des données est accessible sans restrictions
	Accessibles après une période d'embargo
	Accès sous condition indéterminée (ex. "contacter le déposant")
	Accès aux seules métadonnées
	Aucun accès
Les données sont-elles disponibles sans outils et protocoles spécifiques ?	A travers des services web (API)
	Par consultation ou téléchargement depuis un site web
	Par transfert individuel à l'usager
	Données non disponibles

Les métadonnées resteront-elles accessibles même après suppression des données ?	Oui
	Non
	Incertain
...Interopérables	
Dans quel type de formats les données sont-elles stockées ?	Structuré, standard, ouvert, lisible par les machines
	Structuré, standard, ouvert, non lisible par les machines
	Majoritairement dans un format propriétaire
Comment les données sont-elles décrites (vocabulaires contrôlés, ontologies, mots-clés) ?	Standard, ouvert, pourvu d'identifiants uniques liés aux définitions
	Standard, ouvert, sans identifiants
	Descripteurs non standards
	Aucun descripteur pour les données
Les métadonnées sont-elles liées à d'autres données et métadonnées ?	Les métadonnées sont représentées dans un langage lisible par les machines (ex. RDF)
	Les métadonnées comportent des URI renvoyant vers d'autres ressources (données, métadonnées, définitions)
	Aucun lien vers d'autres métadonnées ou données
...Réutilisables	
Quels sont les licences utilisées pour	Licence standard et lisible par les machines

vos données ?	
	Licence standard non intégrée aux métadonnées
	Licence non standard mais lisible par les machines
	Licence non standard et non lisible par les machines
	Aucune licence
Quel est le niveau d'information fourni sur la provenance des données ?	Provenance détaillée et lisible par les machines
	Provenance détaillée en format texte
	Provenance partiellement précisée
	Aucune information sur la provenance

Questionnaire translated from "FAIR self assessment tool" from Australian Research Data Center (<https://ardc.edu.au/resources/working-with-data/fair-data/fair-self-assessment-tool/>)